

Syntheses and Biological Activity of Heterocycles Derived from 4-[5-(2-Furanyl)-4,5-Dihydro-3-Methyl-1H-Pyrazol-1-yl]benzoic Acid

K. S. VARMA and P. S. FERNANDES

Nadkarny-Sacasa Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, St. Xavier's College, Bombay-400 001

Manuscript received 6 August 1982, revised 21 November 1983, accepted 27 February 1984

A series of new compounds viz., 4-[5-(2-furanyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-methyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl]benzoic acid (I); 4-[5-(2-furanyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-methyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl]benzoic acid hydrazide (II); 4-[5-(2-furanyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-methyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl]benzoic acid (phenyl methylene) hydrazide (III); 4-[5-(2-furanyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-methyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl]benzoic acid, 2-[(phenylamino) thiomethyl]hydrazide (IV); 5-[4-(5-(2-furanyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-methyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)phenyl]-2,4-dihydro-4-phenyl-3H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thione (V); 5-[4-(5-(2-furanyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-methyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)phenyl]-N-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine (VI) have been synthesized and some of the compounds have been screened against a few microorganisms for antibacterial activity.

SINCE the discovery of iso-nicotinic acid hydrazide, an effective antitubercular drug, several hydrazides possessing diverse biological activities such as anti-bacterial, anti-inflammatory, anti-hypersensitive, etc. have been reported^{1,2}. In continuation of our earlier work on the synthesis and anti-bacterial screening of some hydrazides^{3,4} and their derivatives as also the synthesis of 1,2,4-triazoles^{5,6}, it was thought of interest to extend such work to the pyrazoline series and study their antibacterial and pharmacological activities.

The present paper deals with the syntheses of few heterocycles derived from 4-[5-(2-furanyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-methyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl]benzoic acid⁷ (I). The acid (I) was converted to its acid hydrazide (II) with a view to synthesize its N-benzylidenes (III) and substituted thiosemicarbazides (IV) by condensing it with a few aryl isothiocyanates. The thiosemicarbazides were then converted to 1,2,4-triazoles (V) and 1,3,4-oxadiazoles (VI). Some of the compounds synthesized were screened for antibacterial activity.

(I) R = -COOH, (II) R = -CONHNH₂, (III) R = -CONHNH=CH-Ar, (IV) R = -CONHNHC(=S)-NHAr

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken in KBr pellets and are expressed in cm^{-1} .

4-[5-(2-Furanyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-methyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl]benzoic acid (I): 4-Hydrazino benzoic acid (0.1 mole) and 1-(2-furanyl)but-1-en-3-one (0.1 mole) were refluxed in ethanol for 6 hr. The precipitated product on cooling the mixture was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, yield 94%, m.p. 222°. (Found: C, 65.97; H, 5.05; N, 10.18. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_8$ requires C, 66.66; H, 5.18; N, 10.37%). IR (KBr): 1670, 1420 (C=O, C-OH of -COOH); 1600 (C=N, pyrazoline); 1175 (C-O-C, furan).

4-[5-(2-Furanyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-methyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl]benzoic acid hydrazide (II): The acid (I) was converted to its hydrazide (II) by the reported methods^{3,4}. It was recrystallised from aqueous methanol, yield 83%, m.p. 140°. (Found: C, 62.92; H, 5.49; N, 19.68. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_8$ requires C, 63.38; H, 5.63; N, 19.71%). IR (KBr): 1705, 1520 (-CONHNH₂).

4-[5-(2-Furanyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-methyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl]benzoic acid (phenyl methylene) hydrazides (III) (Table 1): Equimolar quantities of hydrazide (II) and appropriate aromatic aldehyde were refluxed in ethanol with a few drops of acetic acid for 2 hr. The product separated on cooling, was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, yield 60-80%.

TABLE 1—4-[5-(2-FURANYL)-4,5-DIHYDRO-3-METHYL-1H-PYRAZOL-1-YL]BENZOIC ACID, (PHENYL METHYLENE)-HYDRAZIDE (III)

Sl. No.	Ar	m.p. °C	Yield %	M.F.	N % Found (Calcd.)
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -	208	76	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄	14.96 (15.00)
2.	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	217	81	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₄	14.15 (14.50)
3.	2-OHC ₆ H ₄ -	198	88	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄	13.31 (13.23)
4.	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	211	79	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₄	13.69 (13.93)
5.	C ₄ H ₉ O-(2-furanyl)	205	75	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄	15.34 (15.46)

4-[5-(2-Furanyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-methyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl]benzoic acid, 2-[(phenyl amino)thiomethyl]hydrazide (IV) (Table 2): To a solution of II (0.002 mole) in ethanol (20 ml) was added appropriate aryl isothiocyanate (0.002 mole). The mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. The separated product on cooling was filtered, washed with ether and recrystallised

from ethanol, yield 67-82%. IR (KBr): 1660, 1200 (C=O, C=S).

5-[4-{5-(2-Furanyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-methyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl}phenyl]-2,4-dihydro-4-phenyl-3H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thione (V) (Table 3): The thiosemicarbazide (IV) (0.001 mole) and NaOH (2N, 10 ml) were refluxed for 2 hr. The solution was cooled, filtered and acidified with acetic acid. The precipitated product was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, yield 54-70%. IR (KBr): 1590 (C=N), 2650 (SH).

5-[4-{5-(2-Furanyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-methyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl}phenyl]-N-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine (VI) (Table 4): Thiosemicarbazide (IV) (0.001 mole) was dissolved in cold solution of NaOH (4N, 5 ml). Iodine solution (5%) was then added dropwise with stirring till the colour of iodine persisted. The mixture was refluxed and more iodine solution was added till a permanent tinge of iodine remained. The mixture was cooled and treated with ice-cold water. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed with dilute Na₂S₂O₃ and then with water and

TABLE 2—4-[5-(2-FURANYL)-4,5-DIHYDRO-3-METHYL-1H-PYRAZOL-1-YL]BENZOIC ACID, 2-[(PHENYLAMINO)-THIOMETHYL]HYDRAZIDE (IV)

Sl. No.	Ar	m.p. °C	Yield %	M.F.	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)	
					N	S
6.	C ₆ H ₅ -	181	67	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ S	16.55 (16.70)	7.42 (7.63)
7.	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	183	69	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	15.93 (16.16)	7.07 (7.39)
8.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄ -	196	86	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ SCl	15.10 (15.43)	7.10 (7.05)
9.	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	180	82	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	15.45 (16.59)	6.91 (7.12)

TABLE 3—5-[4-{5-(2-FURANYL)-4,5-DIHYDRO-3-METHYL-1H-PYRAZOL-1-YL}PHENYL]-2,4-DIHYDRO-4-PHENYL-3H-1,2,4-TRIAZOL-3-THIONE (V)

Sl. No.	Ar	m.p. °C	Yield %	M.F.	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)	
					N	S
10.	C ₆ H ₅ -	271	54	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ON ₂ S	17.30 (17.45)	7.61 (7.98)
11.	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	235	61	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ ON ₂ S	16.55 (16.86)	7.50 (7.71)
12.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄ -	256	76	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ ON ₂ S	15.81 (16.07)	7.04 (7.34)
13.	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	240	70	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ S	15.93 (16.24)	7.13 (7.42)

TABLE 4—5-[4-{5-(2-FURANYL)-4,5-DIHYDRO-3-METHYL-1H-PYRAZOL-1-YL}PHENYL]-N-PHENYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOL-2-AMINE (VI)

Sl. No.	Ar	m.p. °C	Yield %	M.F.	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
14.	C ₆ H ₅ -	245	46	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂	68.15 (68.57)	4.63 (4.98)	17.93 (18.18)
15.	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	210	59	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂	69.28 (69.17)	5.10 (5.26)	17.14 (17.54)
16.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄ -	203	65	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	62.33 (62.63)	4.44 (4.74)	16.40 (16.60)
17.	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	135	61	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂	66.40 (66.50)	5.21 (5.06)	16.51 (16.86)

recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, yield 41-64%. IR (KBr) : 1600 (C=N) ; 3320 (NH).

Screening for antibacterial activity :

All the compounds were screened *in vitro* against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The antibacterial activity of the compounds was tested by the ditch-plate technique⁹ using concentrations of 1 mg and 2 mg/ml.

The hydrazide (II) was active against all organisms used except *P. aeruginosa* and *S. typhi*. Compound nos. 2, 8, 11 and 12 were active against all except *P. aeruginosa*. Compound nos. 3, 6, 9, 10 and 16 were inactive against all the organisms employed. Compound Nos. 4, 7 and 15 were active against *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis*.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Mr. R. K. Sen and (Miss) A. D'Silva, Department of Microbiology, St.

Xavier's College for carrying out antibacterial screening of the compounds and to Prof. V.V. Nadkarny for useful discussions.

References

1. N. P. BUU-HOI, N. D. XUONG, N. H. NAM, F. BINON and R. ROYER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 1358.
2. K. REDDA, L. A. CORLETO and E. N. KNAUS, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1979, **22**, 1079.
3. P. S. FERNANDES and V. V. NADKARNY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1059.
4. P. S. FERNANDES, A. M. RAJJI, K. RANE and A. G. JOSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 676.
5. P. S. FERNANDES, R. D'COSTA and V. V. NADKARNY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 780.
6. P. S. FERNANDES, J. G. COUTINHO, K. B. COELHO and V. V. NADKARNY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 498.
7. K. S. VARMA, Part II of Ph.D. Thesis, University of Bombay, 1982.
8. C. H. COLLINS and P. M. LYNE, "Microbiological Methods", 3rd Ed., Butterworths, London, 1970, p. 424.